

Measuring Productivity Using Linear Regression Technique in Labour-Intensive Construction Projects in Zambia

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Abstract

Labour Productivity has been identified as a major contributor to the decline in the construction sector's growth. The decline has been attributed to lack of control of the labour productivity constraint factors used in the prediction improvements not been fully explored. The research aimed at identifying and assessing constraint factors contributing to diminishing labour productivity in construction projects. The research was cross-sectional using quantitative methods. Data was collected using 150 structured questionnaires administered to critical site personnel. A response rate of 81% was obtained and 122 respondents confirmed the extent of the impact of the factors through a survey questionnaire. The scale was tested using Cronbach's Alpha which was found to be > 0.8. The primary data which was obtained from questionnaires was analysed using descriptive statistics. Through the research, 36 key constraint factors of labour productivity were identified and grouped them as project-related, management-related, labour-related and industry-related. The top five ranked constraint factors included: challenging working heights, poor time planning and scheduling, poor sequencing of work, lack of experience and skill, and poor working environment.

Keywords: *Productivity; Labour Intensive Projects; Performance; Management*

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Globally, the construction sector has been identified as a key contributor to national growth (NCC, 2004). The sector has been directly linked to the growth of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Research conducted in the developing countries reviewed that the overall GDP receives a large contribution from the construction sector, making it the highest contributor to national growth (Alaloul et al, 2021). Kakoma and Muya (2016) agree that with the size of the construction industry has an impact on the growth any nation. It is expected that a boom in the construction sector would bust the country's economy (Lewis, 2009). Hence, the influence of the performance of the construction sector on the economic development of a nation cannot be overemphasized. The contribution of the construction industry to the GDP growth means that it also helps to set up infrastructure which supports other economic sectors. As a result, the sector has capability to create employment as noted by Dainty et al. (2004), Bodapati (2003) and Chen (1998) cited by Muya et al (2007). Kirchberger (2020) agreed that the construction sector is in a better position to sustain the strategic sectors of a country's economy while employing a huge labour force. Henstridge and Rweyemanu (2017) cited that construction has an impact on the labour market for a range of semi-skilled and skilled workers especially construction workers, bricklayers, metal workers, carpenters, plumbers, and electricians.

50 Consequently, the capacity and efficiency of the sector are important to the
51 national development goal, especially in developing countries.

52 However, Kirchberger (2020) bemoaned the consequences of a poorly functioning
53 construction sector. The study reviewed that such a sector would tend to translate
54 into high prices, resulting in low levels of output per expenditure. Furthermore, such
55 economies tend to have low local capacity and are required to import construction
56 services from foreign firms, thereby limiting local employment generation,
57 productivity and local content. The construction sector has consistently been a victim
58 of countless challenges, including internal and external pressures that upset and
59 impact its performance (Ofori, 2000). The delivery of public infrastructure is
60 challenged by poor performance, over expenditure and poor delivery (Ministry of
61 Works and Supply, 2006), though Ahmed et al (2002) argued that delays in
62 completion, cost and time overruns of construction projects are a world-wide
63 phenomenon.

64 Labour-intensive construction methods have been used in developing infrastructure
65 works for a long time since they provide employment to local people while
66 contributing to the growth of organisations and nations. During the process, a lot of
67 materials manufactured locally are used, hence creating a higher requirement for
68 products and services than highly mechanized projects (Thwala, 2007). Becker (1964)
69 noted that labour productivity is one of the critical variables impacting the
70 competitive capability of an organization as well as a nation. However, labour
71 productivity has not been agreed to be a crucial contributor to the growth of
72 organizations in most developing countries (Heshmati and Rashidghalam (2018),
73 thereby making it a critical risk in construction projects.

74
75 Many times, challenges related to productivity lead to cost, quality and time losses
76 on construction projects. According to Abdelaal et al, (2015), the effects may be
77 evidenced through "lack of coordination, unidentified scope leading to poor
78 planning, lack of monitoring and control, unrealistic schedules, poor implementation,
79 and incorrect resource allocation" among other reasons. Globally, there is a general
80 worry about the vulnerability of projects in terms of time and cost overrun due to
81 problems of productivity. There is a need to come up with methods to deal with
82 productivity on site and develop a structured and coherent methodological
83 approach to evaluate and monitor productivity levels in construction projects
84 concerning labour and equipment. A model that would predict productivity would
85 not only benefit construction companies but also client organizations, thereby
86 bringing back the lost confidence and stimulating GDP growth. The overall aim of
87 the study was to develop a model for predicting construction labour productivity in
88 Zambia. The model outputs could serve as a basis for encouraging construction
89 organizations to work towards enhancing productivity and competitiveness in
90 labour-intensive projects. The output of the study would serve as a basis for planning
91 infrastructure projects and improving delivery. To achieve the main objective, the
92 following specific objectives were considered:

- 93 i) Identify the factors affecting productivity in labour-intensive construction
94 projects,
- 95 ii) Evaluate the extent of the impact of each factor; and

96 iii) Develop a mathematical model for measuring labour productivity and validate
97 it.

98 **2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW**

99 **2.1 Understanding Labour Productivity in the Construction Sector**

100 Globally, it has been identified that productivity is a crucial component of an
101 organization's growth strategy in its operations. It plays a key role at macro and micro
102 levels affecting the firm's performance. Productivity can be used as a measure to
103 benchmark against world-class entities with best practices. Murari and Joshi (2019)
104 described labour productivity as a measure of improving the production of the
105 construction sector. They argue that it reflects the productivity of construction
106 workers which eventually affects the overall project performance. Lim (1996) also
107 defined productivity as the ratio of output to input while Chia et al., (2014) agreed
108 that productivity is defined as the ratio of product output to input resources. Yi and
109 Chan (2014) argued that labour productivity can be viewed as a concept used to
110 measure the efficiency of the worker and is calculated as the value of output
111 produced by a worker per unit of time, such as an hour.

112

113 Productivity rates are used by project managers during planning and scheduling to
114 reduce labour costs and improve the performance of workers (Alinaitwe et al., 2007).
115 The construction sector gradually created a significant labour productivity gap
116 compared to other industries over the past five decades and it is estimated that only
117 50% of the total construction time is productive thereby impacting the overall
118 performance (Horman and Kenley, 2005). Labour is a major component in the
119 construction industry that accounts for 40% of the total cost of a project (Halwatura,
120 2015). Therefore, improving labour productivity is an effective approach to improving
121 the overall productivity of the industry.

122

123 The focus of this research was to review labour-intensive construction projects which
124 utilize construction workers and less of equipment. The research focussed on Small
125 and Medium Enterprise contractors that used labour-intensive methods as a tool for
126 productivity due to their inability to own equipment. Labour-intensive methods are
127 defined as "programmes that generate more direct and indirect local employment
128 opportunities and income by using locally available input, creating a greater
129 demand for local products and services than do high-technology programmes
130 reliant on imported technology and equipment" (Thwala, 2007).

131

132 **2.2 Measurement of Labour Productivity on Construction Projects**

133 Previous studies at the industry level have mostly focused on productivity
134 measurement (Vogl and Abdel-Wahab 2015), long-term productivity trends (Borg
135 and Song 2014) and measured total (e.g. Hu and Liu 2017) or partial factor
136 productivity, in particular, labour productivity (Choi et al, 2021). However, there has
137 been a revealed evolution of productivity indices over time across several
138 economies. Mostly, this is because productivity rates differ between projects due to
139 the varying environments, characteristics and project management efforts for each
140 project. Unfortunately, there is no model to assist stakeholders in planning their

141 productivity. The existing models have shortcomings as identified by Zhao et al.,
142 (2014). Therefore, there is a need to explore parameters and strategies for predicting
143 improvements more accurately.

144 With the increase in competition in the construction industry, every organization is
145 required to measure its performance (Kulatunga et al., 2005). The measurement of
146 performance has become the “language of progress of an organization” (Rose,
147 1995) and no improvement in any business can be gained unless there is a
148 measurement of its performance (Baldwin et al., 2001). Neely (1998) defined
149 performance measurement as the “process of quantifying past actions, where
150 measurement is the process of quantification and past actions determine current
151 performance.” Therefore, there is a need to measure the performance of contractors
152 in the construction process and find out the factors affecting it. According to Cheung
153 et al. (2006), project performance can be investigated and evaluated using a large
154 number of performance indicators, expressed by factors such as time, cost, quality,
155 client satisfaction, client changes, and health and safety.

156

157 **2.3 Challenges and Risks Associated with Construction Labour Productivity**

158 Risks and challenges associated with productivity usually lead to cost and time losses
159 on construction projects. Abdelaal et al, (2015) relate that the effects may be
160 evidenced through “lack of coordination, unidentified scope leading to poor
161 planning, lack of monitoring and control, unrealistic schedules, poor implementation,
162 and incorrect resource allocation” among other reasons. Globally, there is a general
163 worry about the vulnerability of projects in terms of time and cost overrun due to
164 problems of productivity. Therefore, there is a need to come up with methods to deal
165 with productivity on-site and ensure that it is accurately measured.

166 Unlike other sectors, one of the critical challenges in the construction sector is the
167 divergences in the productivity measurements of labour. While others apply time
168 (hours-based), it is common for others to measure productivity using employment-
169 based measures of labour input (O’Grady and McCabe, 2021). For example, a
170 company may base their production rate on a 40-hour-per-week calculation for
171 critical trades, while others may base it on a 10hrs/day production. It is also common
172 in residential construction to account for production based on a piece-rate payment
173 where hours typically exceed 40 per week. Since 25-35% of construction labour is self-
174 employed, estimates of average weekly hours are problematic for this group. Easier
175 methods of measurement are required. Below is a review of the challenges of labour
176 productivity in different countries.

177

178 In South Africa, Sibiyi, et al. (2015) identified several factors affecting the
179 performance of the construction industry. These ranged from the project level to the
180 national level and relate to the low capacity and capability of the local contractors
181 and consultants caused by a weak resource base and inadequate experience. The
182 industry has been affected by inadequate and erratic work opportunities,
183 inappropriate contract packaging of works which favour foreign firms in donor-
184 funded projects, low public investment in infrastructure projects over-dependence
185 on donor funding and inefficient and non-transparent procurement systems due to
186 corruption and financial mismanagement in public/private sectors. There is also a

187 lack of supportive institutional mechanisms in terms of financial credit facilities,
188 equipment for hire and professional development. A study conducted by
189 Makulsawatudom et al. (2004) in Thailand revealed that the construction sector
190 faces many challenges resulting in low productivity. Like many countries, the sector
191 has been dominated by a large number of small companies whose contribution to
192 the market share is only 9.9% compared to a few large companies with 21.5%.
193 Responses from 34 project managers revealed challenges relating to a lack of
194 materials, incomplete drawings, incompetent supervisors, poor communication,
195 instruction time, poor site layouts, and delays in undertaking inspections and rework.

196 Almamlook et al. (2020) undertook a study of factors affecting labour productivity in
197 Libya. The factors were grouped into management, technological and
198 human/labour. The most significant factors identified were lack of supervision, lack of
199 experience and skilled labour, Construction technology, coordination among
200 construction industry disciplines and errors in design drawings. These findings agree
201 with the factors identified in Thailand.

202 **2.4 Construction Labour Productivity in Zambia**

203 In Zambia, construction firms are graded according to their capacity to deliver a
204 project based on the previous contracts, level of access to credit, number of
205 professional and technical staff, financial position and their state of technology. The
206 grading uses Arabic numerals, with 1 being the highest attainable and 6 being the
207 entry or lowest grade. According to NCC (2021), a total of 10,245 construction firms
208 were registered in 2021. Figure 1 and Table 1 depict that the building category (B)
209 had the highest number of registered construction firms at 3,885. Further, Figure 1 and
210 Table 1 show that grades 4, 5 and 6 accounted for the highest number of registered
211 construction firms in the building category with 9 per cent (2411), 23 per cent (871)
212 and 62 per cent (351) respectively. Additionally, grades 4, 5 and 6 also presented the
213 highest number of registered construction firms in the civil engineering category with
214 8 per cent (120), 20 per cent (287) and 63 per cent (917) respectively. This confirmed
215 that the construction industry in Zambia is predominantly labour-intensive, mostly
216 composed of Small and Medium Enterprise construction firms.

217 With the growing demand for construction services in Zambia, the levels of
218 productivity in the sector will demand more attention from policymakers than before
219 (Cheelo and Liebenthal, 2020). There has been a growing need to monitor the
220 impact of the factors driving construction productivity and infrastructure
221 development in Zambia to improve the efficiency levels of the country's investments
222 (Hernesniemi et al, 1996; Porter, 1990). It is evident that investing in innovation,
223 research and development can enhance productivity and promote manufacturing
224 competitiveness (Mattoussi and Ayadi 2017).

225 There is little evidence of research conducted on the extent of the impact of factors
226 on the labour productivity of construction projects in Zambia. Sampa (2016)
227 undertook a study to evaluate the effects of workers' welfare facilities on productivity
228 in Zambian construction industry. It identified poor employment conditions, lack of
229 basic site amenities and inadequate welfare facilities as some of the factors
230 affecting productivity. The other existing literature discusses the factors affecting the
231 performance of the construction industry including Zulu and Chileshe (2008) who

232 argued that the construction industry in Zambia performs below expectations and
233 that nothing can be learned from local ongoing projects that have not been
234 completed or have been delayed. They concluded that the poor performance of
235 contractors had huge implications on the competitiveness of their businesses.

236 Ngomi (2017) identified poor project financing, lack of supervision skills, lack of tools
237 and lack of capacity as the major indicators of poor performance in Zambia. Further,
238 poor financial management, lack of communication on technical matters, lack of
239 project management skills and failure to provide a safe working environment were
240 identified by Sylvia (2017) as factors inhibiting the performance of construction
241 projects in Zambia.

242 **2.5 Importance of labour productivity**

243 Research reviews a profound interaction among the various factors influencing
244 labour productivity. It explains important interrelationships and dependencies
245 between different factors, offering frameworks for comprehending the interactions
246 between the variables and enabling more focused interventions and productivity-
247 boosting tactics on building sites.

248 Some scholars' insights go beyond simple identification of factors, to suggesting
249 possible remedies to lessen the detrimental effects of specific factors on worker
250 productivity. For construction professionals looking for evidence-based methods to
251 maximise worker performance and efficiency, measurement is the way to go. Several
252 researchers have made a significant contribution to the field with their thorough
253 investigation of the variables influencing labour productivity in the construction
254 sector.

255 Further, some research at the industry level focused on productivity measurement
256 (Vogl and Abdel-Wahab, 2015), long-term productivity trends (Allmon et al, 2000)
257 and measured total (Gal, 2013) or partial or single-factor productivity, in particular,
258 labour productivity (Choi et al, 2016), and revealed the evolution of productivity
259 indices over time across several economies or nations. Productivity rates differ
260 between projects due to the varying environments, characteristics and project
261 management efforts for each project. There is a need to explore parameters and
262 strategies for predicting improvements more accurately (Yi and Chan, 2014) as there
263 are shortcomings in the existing models as identified by Zhou and He (2013). Mirahadi
264 and Zayedi (2016) made a substantial contribution to the body of knowledge of the
265 variables affecting worker productivity in the construction sector. The study carefully
266 identified and examined skill levels, working conditions, and project management
267 techniques as some of the crucial factors. Their work provided a fundamental
268 resource for researchers and construction professionals tackling labour-related issues
269 by elucidating the complexities of these factors.

270
271 Studies conducted by Atta (2012) have demonstrated the critical role that the
272 physical workspace plays in determining worker productivity in the construction
273 sector. An environment that is safe, orderly, and supportive of effective work
274 practices is created in the workplace. The general seamless operation of
275 construction projects is facilitated by adequate accessibility to work areas, well-

276 maintained equipment, and effective layout planning. It reduces downtime and
277 guarantees that workers can move between tasks with ease when tools and
278 materials are arranged in an accessible manner.

279 **2.6 Labour productivity factors**

280 Productivity is understood to be the outcome of several interrelated factors. The
281 literature identifies various factors that affect labour productivity in construction
282 projects in different parts of the globe. The unique nature and character of labour-
283 intensive construction projects make the process be executed over a long period
284 while going through a rigorous procedure having several components. Hence,
285 labour productivity is affected by numerous factors. The study identified 36 factors
286 through a thorough analysis of the literature on labour productivity in the construction
287 sector, non-participant observations and interviews. Situated at the centre of
288 economic growth, the construction industry is complex, requiring new approaches
289 to improvement, creative forecasting models, inventive benchmarking programmes,
290 and a sophisticated comprehension of the variables affecting worker productivity.
291 This review captures the complexity of the industry's pursuit of increased productivity
292 and effectiveness.

293 The probability of occurrence and the impact on labour productivity in construction
294 projects was examined. The identified factors were divided into four groups as shown
295 in Table 2. The factors influencing labour productivity were identified, highlighting the
296 complex interactions between different components in construction projects.
297 Understanding the subtleties of labour dynamics lays the groundwork for targeted
298 interventions and strategic enhancements, ranging from the physical work
299 environment to project planning and scheduling. The literature review highlights how
300 critical it is to identify and address potential productivity barriers to create an
301 atmosphere that supports the growth of the construction workforce.

302

303 **3.0 METHODS**

304 This study adopted mixed research where quantitative and qualitative methods were
305 used as the main techniques. Statistics were drawn from quantitative data, while
306 human experiences and contextual depth through case study observations were
307 added to the findings by qualitative data. A more thorough and rigorous
308 investigation of productivity enhancement in the construction sector was
309 guaranteed by the combination of these approaches. This study was designed to
310 address the research questions identified and achieve the objectives outlined. It was
311 considered essential to obtain a full understanding of the study by setting out the
312 various elements in a logical sequence, to avoid misunderstanding at any point in
313 the research. The problem statement aims and objectives of the research were
314 therefore stated at the outset. The present study employs a multi-paradigmatic
315 approach that integrates qualitative and quantitative methodologies to conduct an
316 exhaustive investigation of productivity enhancement in the construction sector. In
317 addition to administering a structured questionnaire to managers and handymen
318 engaged in these particular construction activities, the research design incorporates
319 a case study on concreting and bricklaying.

320 To obtain comprehensive qualitative insights from important stakeholders, interviews
321 were conducted on labour productivity improvement in bricklaying and concreting
322 within the construction industry. A selection of professionals, including project
323 managers, site engineers, bricklayers and handymen directly involved in concreting
324 and bricklaying projects, was made based on their roles and areas of expertise. A
325 variety of participant representation was sought to encompass a wide range of
326 viewpoints and experiences within the construction industry. Non-probability
327 sampling technique was used for the questionnaire survey since it involved selecting
328 participants for special situations. A purposive sampling approach was adopted with
329 an emphasis on judgment sampling due to the selection of unique cases that are
330 especially informative, and since the researcher wanted to identify particular types
331 of cases for in-depth investigation. The purpose was to gain a deeper understanding
332 of those particular types of cases (Neuman, 2009). A total of 150 participants were
333 targeted.

334 Case studies of three labour-intensive construction projects were undertaken. The
335 studies were aimed at investigating the factors affecting the labour productivity of
336 construction workers. Where possible, case studies highlighted how labour is
337 managed given different project environments, levels of skills, and availability of
338 resources and tools. Care was taken to differentiate these experiences according
339 to the project environments of the different sites. This was to avoid the adoption and
340 recommendation of unworkable and unrealistic principles.

341
342 Data consisted of a total of 108 hours of field-noted observation of construction
343 processes, 26 hours of video-recorded construction activities, 23 individual interviews
344 of Project Managers and Site Engineers (with duration ranging from 27 to 54 minutes),
345 and 67 reviewed documents. In supporting the data collection tools, all these
346 separate data items were incorporated into the interview and questionnaire survey.

347 348 **3.1 Methods of Analysis**

349 Data collected from the survey was analysed using descriptive statistical techniques.
350 The quantitative data was analysed statistically to find trends, relationships, and
351 statistically significant factors influencing productivity in these construction activities.
352 An advanced and accurate analysis method was needed to arrange the large body
353 of data in a systematic, fast and reliable way. For this purpose, the computer software
354 Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) and Excel were chosen as the best
355 options available. Regression and correlation are two of the techniques that were
356 used for data analysis.

357
358 The research used the regression analysis method to evaluate the extent of the
359 impact of factors on the labour productivity of construction workers in Zambia. A
360 strata ordinal logistic regression model that focused on the interrelated connection
361 between general factors (dependent variables) such as labour productivity of
362 workers in a construction project and effect factors (independent variables) was
363 used. A 5-step process was adopted as follows:

364 **Step 1: Determining the research model**

365 Poole and O'Farrell (1971) reviewed an ordinal logistic regression model that focuses
366 on the interrelated connection between general factors (dependent variables) such
367 as labour productivity of workers in a construction project and effect factors
368 (independent variables) can be defined as:

369 **Logit (P(Y ≤ j)) = $\beta_{j0} + \beta_{j1} X_1 + \beta_{j2} X_2 + \beta_{j3} X_3 + \beta_{j4} X_4 + \dots + \beta_{jp} X_p$**

370 Where: β is a free coefficient

371 $\beta_{j0}, \beta_{j1}, \beta_{j2}, \dots, \beta_{jp}$ are free coefficients

372 $X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, \dots, X_p$ are independent variables (factor effects components)

373 Y are dependent variables (labour productivity of workers in construction
374 projects)

375 In other tools like stata ordinal logistic regression model is parameterized as shown
376 below;

377 **Logit (P(Y ≤ j)) = $\beta_{j0} - \beta_{j1} X_1 - \beta_{j2} X_2 - \beta_{j3} X_3 + \beta_{j4} X_4 - \dots - \beta_{jp} X_p$**

378 The model in normal regression adds the coefficients for the explanatory variable to
379 the intercept to obtain the predicted outcome (e.g. $Y = a + bX$) while in ordinal
380 regression the model is parameterized as $Y = a - bX$.

381 Where ' a ' is the Y-intercept

382 ' b ' is the coefficient of odds or the Beta Coefficients.

383 However, the predicted values do not change but it is done so to mean the following:
384 Positive coefficients mean that higher values of the explanatory variable are
385 associated with higher outcomes while negative coefficients mean that higher
386 values of the explanatory variable are associated with lower outcomes.

387

388 **Step 2: Design of questionnaire survey form and data collection**

389 A questionnaire survey was designed to evaluate the impact of the key factors. To
390 obtain a conclusive result on factors affecting labour productivity, 36 factors in four
391 groups, identified in literature review and interviews were subjected to a
392 questionnaire survey. Respondents were asked to rate the occurrence of the factors
393 that affected labour productivity based on the Likert scale of 1 to 5. The size of the
394 samples for the quantitative analysis was calculated using a formula for regression
395 analysis: **$n \geq 50 + 10 * p$** .

396 Where:

397 **n** is the size of the sample

398 **p** is the number of independent variables in the model.

399 Therefore, the indispensable size of the sample is $n \geq 50 + 10 \cdot 4 = 50 + 10 \cdot 4 = 90$ (Austin
400 and Steyerberg, 2015).

401

402 **Step 3: Testing the reliability of the scale**

403 Cronbach's coefficient Alpha was tested to determine the internal consistency and
404 reliability of the questionnaire. The reliability test conducted using Cronbach Alpha
405 has standardized values which are used as a control for comparison of the findings
406 (George and Mallery, 2003). Coefficients less than 0.5 were unacceptable, between
407 0.5 and 0.6 were poor, between 0.7 and 0.8 were acceptable, between 0.8 and 0.9
408 were good and greater than 0.9 were considered excellent.

409

410 **Step 4: Determining the influence of each factor**

411 Through an analysis of regression, the influence of each factor was determined
412 through coefficients. Based on the equation, positive coefficients meant that higher
413 values of the explanatory variable were associated with higher outcomes while
414 negative coefficients meant that higher values of the explanatory variable were
415 associated with lower outcomes. The higher coefficient depicted the significant
416 effect on the overall factors of that factor. The coefficient has a valuation within -1
417 and can be defined as:

- 418 a) If the is greater than 0, then there is a positive correlation relationship between
419 independent and dependent variables.
- 420 b) If the value β is less than 0, then there is a negative correlation relationship
421 between independent and dependent variables.
- 422 c) If the value β is closer to 1, the more coherent the correlation relationship
423 between independent and dependent variables is.
- 424 d) If the value β is closer to 0, the lower the correlation relationship between
425 independent and dependent variables is.

426

427 **Step 5: Development of a mathematical formulae model for measuring labour** 428 **productivity**

429 i) Labour Productivity Regression Model (equation) with actual parameters

$$430 \text{Logit } (P(Y \leq j)) = \beta_j0 - \beta_j1 X1 - \beta_j2 X2 - \beta_j3 X3 - \beta_j4 X4 - \dots - \beta_jp Xp$$

431 Where: Y are dependent variables (labour productivity of workers in construction
432 projects)

433 β is a free coefficient

434 $\beta_j0, \beta_j1, \beta_j2, \dots, \beta_jp$ are free coefficients

435 $X1, X2, X3, X4, \dots, Xp$ are independent variables (factor effects components)

436 $X1$: Management-related factors $\beta = 27.10972$

437 $X2$: Project-related factors $\beta = -88.1485$

438 X3: Labour-related factors $\beta = 62.37609$

439 X4: Industry-related factors $\beta = 69.02975$

440

441 **Productivity Level_{predicted} = 140.5665 – 27.10972 * Management-related factors –**
442 **(-88.1485) *Project-related factors – 62.37609 * Labour-**
443 **related factors – 69.02975 * Industry-related factors**

$$\text{Formulae: } Y = 140.5665 - 27.10972_1 - (-88.1485)_2 - 62.37609_3 - 69.02975_4$$

444

445 Based the results, it must be understood that Exp (B) or odds ratio is the predicted
446 change in odds for a unit increase in the predictor. The “Exp” implies the exponential
447 value of B, hence, when Exp (B) is less than 1, increasing values of the variable
448 correspond to the decreasing odds of the event’s occurrence. When Exp (B) is
449 greater than 1, increasing values of the variable corresponds to increasing odds of
450 the event’s occurrence.

451 Therefore, if we subtract 1 from the odds ratio and multiply by 100, we get the
452 percentage change in odds of the dependent variable having a value of 1.

453 *ii)* Application of the Labour Productivity Regression Model

454 a) Regression Equation Beta Coefficients (overall Model without Interaction)

455 **Productivity Level_{predicted} = 5.705 – 0.0255 * Management Related Factors – (-**
456 **0.0745) * Project-related factors – (-0.00756) * Labour-**
457 **related factors – (-0.2526) * Industry-related factors**

458 When we plug in the values for independent variables (management-related factor
459 say Poor site management practices = 1; project-related factor say Inefficiency of
460 Equipment or tools = 0; Labour related factor say years of experience and skill = 10
461 and Industry related factor say Poor working environment = 0) we can predict the
462 value of productivity level.

463 **i.e. Y = 5.705 – 0.0255₁ – (-0.0745)₂ – (-0.00756)₃ – (-0.2526)₄**

464 **Productivity Level_{predicted} = 5.705 – 0.0255 * 1 – (-0.0745) * 0 – (-0.00756) * 10 – (-**
465 **0.2526) * 0**

466 **Productivity Level_{predicted} = 5.75516**

467

468 b) Labour Productivity Regression Equation B estimates (overall Model with
469 Interaction Effect)

470 **Productivity Level_{predicted} = 140.5665 – 27.10972 * Management-related factors –**
471 **(-88.1485) *Project-related factors – 62.37609 * Labour-**
472 **related factors – 69.02975 * Industry-related factors**

473 **i.e. $Y = 140.5665 - 27.10972_1 - (-88.1485_2 - 62.37609_3 - 69.02975_4$**

474 When we plug in the values for independent variables (management-related factor
 475 say Poor site management practices = 1; project-related factor say Inefficiency of
 476 Equipment or tools = 0; Labour related factor say years of experience and skill = 10
 477 and Industry related factor say Poor working environment = 0) we can predict the
 478 value of productivity level.

479 **iii) Odd Ratios**

480 The higher odds are associated with the increasing influence of an independent
 481 variable (factor) on agreeing that productivity levels (dependent variable) are highly
 482 affected by the factor. While the lower odds imply that the increasing influence of
 483 an independent variable (factor) has a reducing effect (disagree) on the
 484 dependent variable.

485 **iv) Interaction Effect**

486 Where the codes represented above for the (dependent variable 1 = Strongly
 487 Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Moderately Agree; 4 = Agree; and 5 = Strongly Agree)
 488 while (Independent Variable codes 1 = Little or No Influence; 2 = Some Influence; 3 =
 489 Average Influence; 4 = Strong Influence; 5 = Very Strong Influence).

491 • Little or No Influence = Productivity Level_{predicted} = $140.5665 - 27.10972*1 - (-$
 492 $88.1485) *1 - 62.37609*1 - 69.02975*1.$

494 • Little or No Influence = Productivity Level_{predicted} = 70.19944

496 • Some Influence = $140.5665 - 27.10972*2 - (-88.1485) *2 - 62.37609*2 - 69.02975*2$
 497 Some Influence = Productivity Level_{predicted} = -0.16762

499 • Average Influence = Productivity Level_{predicted} = $140.5665 - 27.10972*3 - (-$
 500 $88.1485) *3 - 62.37609*3 - 69.02975*3.$

502 Therefore, Average Influence = Productivity Level_{predicted} = -70.5347

504 • Strong Influence = Productivity Level_{predicted} = $140.5665 - 27.10972*4 - (-88.1485)$
 505 $*4 - 62.37609*4 - 69.02975*4.$

506 Therefore, Strong Influence = Productivity Level_{predicted} = -140.902

507 • Very Strong Influence = Productivity Level_{predicted} = $140.5665 - 27.10972*5 - (-$
 508 $88.1485) *5 - 62.37609*5 - 69.02975*5.$

509 Therefore, Very Strong Influence = Productivity Level_{predicted} = -211.269

510 The significant positive effect highlights how several factors work together to shape
 511 the productivity landscape as a whole and provides an important starting point for
 512 understanding how the independent variables work together.

513 The results show how several elements interact to determine productivity levels in
514 labour-intensive construction projects. Overall, productivity outcomes are
515 significantly shaped by the complex interactions between labour-related factors,
516 industry-related factors, management-related factors and project-related factors.
517 Each group factor contributes substantially to the production landscape despite
518 having different coefficients, highlighting the complexity of the construction sector.

519 The importance of good management practices is especially noteworthy, as
520 evidenced by the fact that they rank highest among independent variables. This
521 emphasizes how crucial skillful management techniques are to maximize project
522 performance and productivity.

523 Even with a negative coefficient, project-related factors have a significant effect on
524 production. This subtlety highlights that to maximize overall productivity results,
525 customized considerations about project-specific variables are necessary.

526 The labour-related factors highlight the significance of resolving labour-related issues
527 and maximizing workforce components for increased project productivity. The report
528 emphasizes how important it is for building firms to fund staff development initiatives,
529 such as providing training and creating a happy workplace. Industry factors, which
530 ranked fourth, emphasize how important it is to consider external industry-specific
531 factors for the best productivity outcomes. For a comprehensive understanding of
532 production dynamics and strategic decision-making, this external perspective is
533 essential.

534 **3.2 Validation of the model**

535 The LPRM was validated using practitioners within the Zambian construction industry.
536 The process focused on the validity, legitimacy and functionality of the model. A total
537 of 10 directors in construction firms were targeted in the validation exercise.
538 Responses were received from all the directors. The respondents were availed of the
539 model to conduct their assessment. A brief overview of the model was presented to
540 the participants before the commencement of the assessment. The model and
541 results are presented in the subsections below.

542

543 **4.0 DISCUSSION**

544 **4.1 Awareness of Labour Productivity**

545 The findings of the interviews reviewed that the level of awareness of labour
546 production outputs in the construction industry was low at 28%. The findings of this
547 study tend to agree with Enshassi et al, (2007) that there is a need to increase
548 awareness on labour productivity. It is evident that most Governments show little
549 concern about the welfare of workers and contracting companies have little
550 awareness of the impact of factors on labour productivity. It also agrees with the
551 assertions of Hiyassat et al, (2016) that there is a need to raise awareness among
552 engineers and foremen about the importance of labour productivity.

553

554 **4.2 Key Indicators of Labour Productivity**

555 Several studies have reviewed that the labour productivity of construction workers is
556 impacted by a lot of factors (Van, 2016). Researchers tend to agree that there are
557 several studies on the factors affecting labour productivity in the construction sector

558 yet there are many productivity challenges that remain unknown and require further
559 investigations, especially in developing nations (Makulsawatudom and Emsley, 2002;
560 Hai and Tam, 2019).

561

562 There is agreement that policies for increasing labour productivity are not similar for
563 every nation, hence the classification of the factors may vary (Polat and Arditi, 2005).
564 Olomolaiye et al., (1998) confirm that the factors influencing productivity are rarely
565 constant and are likely to differ from one country to another, from one project to
566 another and even within the same project, depending on the environment and
567 circumstances. Herbsman et al., (1990) classified the factors affecting productivity
568 into two main groups: technological and administrative factors. Abdulaziz et al.,
569 (2012) conducted a study in Kuwait with 45 productivity factors, under four main
570 groups, including: management, technological, human/labour and external. Heizer
571 et al, (1990) identified 3 groups including; characteristic factors of work, factors of
572 working conditions and non-productive activities. Jiukun et al, (2009) identified 83
573 factors after investigating 2,000 artisan workers throughout the United States of
574 America. Horner et al (1989) identified 13 factors affecting productivity in
575 construction projects in UK. Absenteeism, number of operations on site, proportions
576 of work subcontracted, site layout, crew size and composition, skill of labour,
577 buildability, quality of supervision, method of working, incentive scheme, complexity
578 of construction information, length of working days and availability of tools were listed
579 as significant factors.

580

581 The viewpoint seems to agree with the findings in this study where 36 key indicators
582 were identified out of which;

- 583 i) Eight were project-related;
- 584 ii) Twelve were management-related;
- 585 iii) Ten were labour-related; and
- 586 iv) Six were industry-related.

587

588 **4.3 Monitoring labour productivity for construction performance in firms**

589 One of the key steps towards maximising labour productivity and overall project
590 efficiency is the adoption of a benchmarking and metrics program for construction
591 performance (Nasir et al., 2012). This helps to improve construction productivity and
592 performance of a project or sector at large. Benchmarking and metrics programs
593 allow construction firms to identify their specific areas of strength and those that
594 require improvement by methodically measuring and assessing a construction
595 project's performance against industry benchmarks (Ibid, 2012). Performance
596 indicators are critical in assessing progress, devising improvements and comparing a
597 company's performance to that of a different organization (Wu et al., 2010).
598 Benchmarking helps the construction industry foster a continuous improvement
599 culture by providing a uniform framework for evaluation. One of the advantages that
600 a benchmarking program has, is to provide construction firms a comparative analysis
601 of their performance against peers in the sector.

602 According to Chukwudi et al. (2022), monitoring and evaluation impact the
603 productivity of employees, hence crucial to the long-term success of an
604 organization. Unfortunately, most of the companies do not measure and monitor the

605 productivity of their workers. Managers do not equally focus on the welfare of their
606 workers, thereby affecting productivity, safety and health (Muhammad et al, 2015).

607 The emphasis on metrics highlights the significance of numerical data in assessing
608 construction performance. Businesses can learn a lot about how efficiently their
609 operations are running by setting up and keeping an eye on key performance
610 indicators. Metrics like project completion times, resource utilisation rates, and safety
611 records offer concrete standards that are useful for assessing performance and
612 providing useful information for streamlining procedures and strategies (Nasir et al,
613 2012).

614 İşgören et al (2009) reviewed the importance of industry cooperation and knowledge
615 exchange in the construction sector as a means of promoting collective excellence.
616 Building projects are complex undertakings that frequently call for the synthesis of
617 knowledge from a range of stakeholders, including suppliers, contractors, engineers,
618 and architects. The establishment of a collaborative culture facilitates the
619 convergence of diverse perspectives and skill sets, thereby promoting innovation
620 and problem-solving on a larger scale.

621 **5.0 CONCLUSIONS**

622 Thirty-six factors were identified from literature review, observations, interviews and
623 questionnaire survey. Thirteen factors namely: poor working environment, lack of
624 experience and skill, overtime working, lack of labour motivation, poor sequencing
625 of work, poor time planning and scheduling, poor site management practices,
626 unsuitable materials, late issuance of construction materials, finance difficulties,
627 working heights, shortage of equipment and tools and poor accessibility and
628 location were identified as those that most impact productivity in labour-intensive
629 construction projects in Zambia. Through an analysis of regression, the influence of
630 each factor was determined through coefficients. Based on the equation, positive
631 coefficients meant that higher values of the explanatory variable were associated
632 with higher outcomes while negative coefficients meant that higher values of the
633 explanatory variable were associated with lower outcomes. The higher coefficient
634 depicted the significant effect on the overall factors of that factor. Management-
635 related factors had the most significant impact on the labour productivity of
636 construction workers in Zambia. The results highlighted the areas that require the
637 attention of management in construction firms.

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